

Prof. Dr. Elisabeth Legge-Schwarzkopf, D.B.E. Kammersängerin
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Madame Yelena Kurdina
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Metropolitan Opera New York
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Zumikon, 16th October 2000

Dear Madame Kurdina,

I thank you very much indeed for drawing my attention to the fact, that Professor John Wustman is going to be seventy! I would be very hurt, if I would not have been asked by you to put my birthday greetings for him into a book, which should be very thick indeed and full of appraisals of most Lieder singers in the USA for the great teacher and accompanist of the last fifty years. For me he played 56 times and most of the programmes were made by my husband, which means, that they contained extremely difficult compositions also for the pianist. We all know that there is nothing easy with what in America you call "concertising". But John Wustman was always making it seem easy..... One of his main tasks in those days was to make a composer like Hugo Wolf much more known and loved by the American public. We all know, that this composer needs a singer and a pianist of the same eagerness, musicality, sense for poetry and quite a lot of technical prowess.

That he was a real comrade in all situations must also be mentioned For his future I have no better idea, than to wish for him many more fine singers - and other musicians - to fill his music-years with much work and much delight! Health is also wanted, by the way.....

Kindest regards,

Yours,

A large, stylized handwritten signature in black ink. The name 'Elisabeth' is written in a cursive script on the left. To its right, the name 'Legge' is written in a larger, more decorative cursive font, with a large loop above the letter 'e'. Below 'Legge', the name 'Schwarzkopf' is written in a similar cursive style, extending across the bottom of the signature area.

Prof. Dr. Elisabeth Legge-Schwarzkopf, D.B.E.